

READING LITERACY CLASSROOM TEACHING THE STUDENT TO THINK INDEPENDENTLY AND TO EXPRESS HIS OPINION

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Abstract. In the article, the methodology of teaching stories and fairy tales in elementary reading literacy classes, teaching the student to think independently and to form the skills of being able to express, explain, give examples, discuss and conclude is mentioned.

Keywords: story, fairy tale, phrase, content, explanatory dictionary, opinion, explanation, attitude, discussion and conclusion.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a systematic process aimed at providing students with in-depth theoretical knowledge, skills and practical skills, as well as forming their general and professional knowledge, skills and abilities, and developing their abilities [1]. In primary grades, students must acquire the following knowledge, skills and competences in reading:

a) on reading technique:

Quantitative index: being able to read 80-90 words per minute. Requirements:

- correct pronunciation of letters;
- read words correctly;
- read fluently and expressively, observing the tone of speech;
- reflect the punctuation marks in the sentence in the pronunciation;
- correct use of counting and separation tones;
- observing word accents;
- following the tone;
- correct pronunciation of scientific terms and symbols.

b) Regarding the ability to understand the content of the text and the opinion of others:

Quantitative indicator: being able to read and retell a 4-5 page text in 10 minutes.

Requirements:

- oral speech should be correct, fluent, clear, understandable and effective;
- fluency of monologic speech;
- clarity of an effective, consistent, logical aspect in dialogic speech[2].

PROBLEM AND SOLUTION:

As a result of various shortcomings in the educational process and teaching methods in schools and other educational institutions, students do not develop independent thinking, they do not have enough preparation to accept rational life solutions. In order to solve these emerging problems, the material-technical and information base of educational institutions will be strengthened, the educational process will be provided with high-quality educational literature and advanced pedagogical technologies. Informatization of the continuing education system is carried out[3].

In order to eliminate the above-mentioned problem among young people, it is necessary to teach the student to think independently and to strengthen self-confidence from the primary school. We can see that the execution of the above decision is ensured in the example of the school textbooks, including the reading literacy textbook, published on the basis of the state educational standards in this 2023-2024 school year.

In reading literacy classes, elementary school students get acquainted with fairy tales and stories from the types of works of art. The tasks given for the fairy tales and stories presented in the textbook encourage the student to think independently, explain his opinion, discuss it, search for the meaning of the words using explanatory dictionaries and draw a conclusion. Starting from the 3rd grade, students are taught to retell the story. On reading

literacy of 3rd grade given that the stories “**Arizachi svetofor**”(Nasiba Erxonova), “**Chin do’st**”(Nasiba Erxonova), “**Tez yordam-yordamga shay**”(Zuhra Ro’ziyeva), “**Igna**”(Hakim Nazir), **Yaxshilik izlagan bola, Do’stlik yo’lagi** and the fairy-tail “**Enajonim ertak aytdi**”(Xudoyberdi To’xtaboyev). First of all, information about the author of the story and fairy tale enriches the mind of the book-loving reader with information about the author of the work. During the open lessons held with the students of 3rd grade the school 45 in Angor district it is clear that the question which is given to “**Arazchi svetofor**” what do you think, did you do the right thing when the traffic light appeared in the story prompts the reader to react to the story, and the question of how you would move if you got stuck at the intersection with these traffic lights prepared the reader for real life. The discussion of the phrases “*manzil tomon oshiqayotgan*”, “*taqdir taqazosi bilan*”, “*ko’zlarini suzib qo’ydi*”, “*tan olgingiz kelmaydi*”, “*labini burgancha o’tib ketibti*” in the article of “**Chin do’st**”, finding answers to proverbs and poetic riddles suitable for the content of the story encouraged students to think creatively. In the story of “**Tez yordam-yordamga shay**” you know, just like people, cars also have professions. The thoughts that there are firemen and paramedics, truckers and street sweepers, soldiers and guards, fighters and athletes among them will make the child feel love for everything around him. Searching for the words *ishtiyiq, maroqli, tob, mobaynida* from the explanatory dictionary and understanding their meanings increases the student's vocabulary and broadens his worldview. We can see that there are new words that we need to learn not only in foreign languages, but also in our own mother tongue, without being surprised that the meaning of **ishpech** in the story of the needle is a tailor's bag in which threads, needles and other necessary things are kept. Did you know that ancient needles were made of stones, animal bones or horns. It is believed that the first steel needle was made in China. Information such as scissors, which were invented almost simultaneously in several countries 3000 years ago, enriches today's generation with historical

knowledge, and the conditions created for them today did not appear by themselves, every makes you appreciate something.

During the lessons, the content of the story of the “**Yaxshilik izlagan bola**” goodness was retold based on planning. Writing the plan on the board helped to keep the content of the text consistent. Students have an understanding of good and bad. Students were taught to think and express their opinions independently by discussing questions with their classmates, explaining their thoughts with examples, and drawing conclusions. Self-confidence was formed. Through the story of the corridor of friendship, the student got information about good and bad neighbors. By answering the question of what other title can be given to the story, the content of the text was discussed and the students were taught to draw a general conclusion[4].

Pupils are taught to think independently and express their opinion by drawing pictures, staging, and continuing the story. Telling stories develops oral speech, enriches children's speech with new words and phrases.

It is necessary to work on proverbs presented in fairy tales, convey the ideas presented in them to the minds of children, develop communicative speech through memorization, and increase the effectiveness of speech. For example, in the fairy tale “**Ziyrak uch yigit**” for grade 4, it is told that the governor praised the intelligence, understanding, and intelligence of the three brothers. The conclusion corresponding to the idea of a fairy tale is expressed by the proverb “**Aql yoshdan, odob boshdan**” If the students understand the meaning of this proverb, they can create and tell a story like the one above. After reading the fairy tale and introducing its content, the students are attracted and surprised and asked the meaning of the words *diqqatini jalb etib, hayratda qolib, asal, yog’, yumronqoziq, pashshalar, chora, zindon, sharob*. The answers are filled in and summarized[5].

The development, prospects, well-being, spiritual growth of every country, its place among the most developed countries in the world depends on educated, high intellectual potential, young people who embody noble qualities in their hearts and minds, mature and perfect in all respects, the destiny of the Motherland. To bring up a devoted, believing generation, to bring up the quality and content of education to the highest levels, first of all, teachers and educational coaches have an honorable and at the same time responsible task.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that in reading literacy classes, children's reading and telling stories is especially important. Teaching the retelling of works of art and staging them, memorizing the poem imposes a great skill and responsibility on the teacher. The more vividly the content of the work of art is expressed by the author, the more expressive and meaningful the speech of the characters participating in it is, it will excite children, develop their feelings, keep the events with the characters of the work in their memory for a long time, and enrich their vocabulary. has a positive effect on the grammatically correct formation of speech. Children can easily answer the teacher's questions about the work, repeat some words and sentences, tell the positive and negative sides of the characters, imitate the teacher and try to imitate their voices. They think independently and can express their thoughts.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Ta'lim to'g'risida"gi qonuni. //Toshkent sh.2020
2. Boshlang'ich ta'lim bo'yicha yangi tahrirdagi davlat ta'lim standarti
3. Kadrlar tayyorlash Milliy dasturi. // Barkamol avlod O'zbekiston taraqqiyotining poydevori. T.: SHarq, 1997.

4. U.B.Aydarova, N.K.Azizova, M.E.Toirova. O'qish savodxonligi. 3-sinf. T.: Novda, 2023
5. M.Umarova, X.Xamraqulova, R.Tojiboyeva. O'qish kitobi 4-sinf T:O'qituvchi,2019
6. Zarnigor, B., & Ruzikulovna, S. D. (2019). Views Of The Great Thinkers Of The East About Education And Perfection Of Human. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 7(12).
7. Бабамуратова, З., & Шаббазова, Д. Р. (2019). ВЗГЛЯДЫ ВЕЛИКИХ МЫСЛИТЕЛЕЙ ВОСТОКА О ВОСПИТАНИИ И СОВЕРШЕНСТВЕ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. Редакционная коллегия: Главный редактор (учредитель) ИП Всяких Максим Владимирович, кандидат экономических наук, 19.
8. Shabbazova , D. (2023). BOSHLANG‘ICH SINIF O‘QUVCHILARI SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISHDA SHAXSIY QADRYATLI YONDASHUV. MONOGRAFIYA. Termiz-2023. Interpretation and Researches, 1(1).
9. Ruzikulovna, S. D. (2021). PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHER AND STUDENT TEACHING ACTIVITIES AND SYSTEM OF PERSONAL VALUES. European Scholar Journal, 2 (7), 32-33.
10. Норқобилова Р. Boshlang ‘ich sinf o ‘quvchilarining ona tilidan iqtidorini diagnostika qilish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish //Общество и инновации. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 1/5. – С. 36-41.
11. Davlatovna N. R. Indikatorlar asosida boshlang ‘ich sinf o ‘quvchilari faoliyatini diagnostika qilishning o ‘ziga xosligi //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1А. – С. 51-55.
12. Norqobilova R. D. USE of diagnostic tests in foreign schools //Results of National Scientific Research International Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 359-364.

13. Abdisamatova M., Norqobilova R. INNOVATSION YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TARBIYA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISH //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 1.

14. Davlatovna N. R. Functions and Principles of Pedagogical Diagnostics //Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 413-416.